

REPORT:

A2.1.3: Guideline for the Integration of Sensors, Actuators, and Fluidic Components in Microfluidic Devices

Work package 2

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A2.1.3 M10	UTwente, Micronit, METU, INESC MN, IPQ, and CEA will develop a guideline for the integration of sensors/actuators and fluidic components in microfluidic devices. It aims to establish best practices for component selection, design considerations, integration techniques and control systems. The guideline will involve input from A2.1.1. and A2.1.2, focusing specifically on compatibility with an emphasis on ISO 22916:2022, and reproducibility while excluding comprehensive device design and applications beyond microfluidics. Results will be used in A4.2.3 (by M9), A4.2.4, A4.3.2.	UTwente, Micronit, METU, INESC MN, IPQ, CEA
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This report was written by:

Name	Institution	e-mail
Vania Silverio	INESC MN	<i>vsilverio@inesc-mn.pt</i>
Elsa Batista	IPQ	<i>ebatista@ipq.pt</i>
Elwin Vrouwe	Micronit	<i>elwin.vrouwe@micronit.com</i>
Ender Yildirim	METU	<i>yender@metu.edu.tr</i>
Remco den Dulk	CEA	<i>remco.dendulk@cea.fr</i>
Joshua Loessberg-Zahl	UTwente	<i>j.t.loessberg-zahl@utwente.nl</i>

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1. Scope

This report provides best practices for the selection, design, integration, and control of sensors, actuators, and fluidic components within microfluidic systems. Emphasizing compatibility and reproducibility, the guidelines align with ISO 22916:2022 standard. The focus remains on ensuring component interoperability and consistent performance, excluding detailed device design and broader application considerations.

2. Introduction

Microfluidic devices rely on precise manipulation and monitoring of fluids at microscale levels. Effective integration of sensors, actuators, and fluidic components is essential for reliable operation, data accuracy, and process reproducibility in microfluidic systems. Standardization, especially adherence to ISO 22916:2022, SEMI MS6, SEMI MS7, SEMI MS9, and SEMI MS11, EC 63177:2024, IEC 62304, IEC 62321, IEC 61499 and IEEE 1451 ensure compatibility, quality, and safety across manufacturing and operational environments.

3. Component Selection

At the start of system development, product specifications are typically documented as user, system, and functional requirements. These subsequently provide a basis for selecting sensors, actuators, and fluidic components by specifying the necessary functions, operating conditions, and performance parameters for these components.

3.1. User requirements

User requirements define high-level selection criteria and constraints. These include for example:

- Cost price to meet the system cost target.
- Physical size and mass (especially relevant for portable systems).
- Power consumption.
- Environmental limits: e.g. acceptable ambient temperature, humidity and pressure during use as well as during storage.
- Shelf life.
- Disposal considerations (particularly relevant for consumable components).

3.2. System requirements

System requirements translate user needs into quantifiable performance specifications:

- Sensor detection limit, accuracy, resolution and dynamic range: Select sensors capable of detecting the required parameters (pressure, temperature, flow rate, analyte concentration, etc.).
- Sensor selectivity.
- Actuator Response Time: Choose actuators with response times suitable for the intended control processes.
- Reproducibility and stability: Components should demonstrate consistent performance over multiple uses during their lifetime.
- Calibration requirements: do sensors and actuators require regular (factory) calibration, what is the interval and procedure.

- Operational lifetime: This should align with reliability and maintenance expectations.

3.3. Compatibility requirements

- Chemical and biological compatibility: Components in contact with the working fluids should be inert or compatible with the fluid to prevent degradation or contamination of the component or fluid.
- Physical and mechanical compatibility: Components should match the physical dimensions of the microfluidic channels and interfaces. Internal dimensions are large enough too to avoid excessive fluid resistance or risk clogging but small enough to avoid excessive internal volume and reagent consumption.
- Use standardized interfaces and footprints where possible to ensure interoperability and long-term availability (e.g. ISO 22916:2022).
- Interference: Components should not interfere with other components (e.g. mechanical interference due to size, blocking optical paths or electromagnetic emission).

3.4. Manufacturing related criteria

- Robustness during manufacturing, including resistance to chemicals, heat, or mechanical stress during integration steps.
- Compatibility with existing production lines, minimizing the need for investment in additional equipment.
- Impact on other manufacturing processes: integration of components should not disrupt concurrent production processes.
- Automation: how much of the integration can be automated.
- Quality control strategy: how is component (integration) quality verified (e.g. incoming inspection, in-process testing or end-of-line checks).

3.5. Component sourcing criteria

- Lead time and supply reliability: Ensure predictable procurement timelines.
- Inventory costs for keeping a sufficient stock of components.
- Availability of interchangeable components from multiple suppliers to reduce supply chain risks and avoid production downtime.
- Supplier quality maturity: prioritize suppliers with established certifications (e.g., ISO 9001, ISO 13485) and a demonstrated track record of reliable performance.

3.6. Standardization and certification

- Prefer components with recognized certifications aligned with relevant ISO, IEC, or regulatory standards (medical, environmental, safety, EMC, etc.), ensuring compliance with safety, quality, and interoperability standards.

4. Design Considerations

This section outlines considerations related to requirement identification, system architecture, interface compatibility, material selection, environmental conditions, and assembly constraints that affect the operation of the integrated setup. The objective is to support the designers in developing the configuration in which the components can be connected, assembled, and operated without compromising fluidic integrity, performance, or reliability.

4.1. Identification of the Requirements

The design shall begin with the identification of the functional and operational requirements of the intended application. Requirements should define the expected behaviour and the components, as well as the constraints affecting interoperability, performance, and reliability. The requirements should include, but is not limited to, the following aspects:

- System function, including the intended purpose and the main functional elements (e.g. sensors, actuators, valves, mixers, etc.),
- Fluid characteristics, including the type of the fluid(s), the viscosity, the density, potential presence of particles (If particles are present, the type of particles such as solid beads, liquid droplets, gaseous bubbles, cells, etc.)
- Flow parameters, including the required flow rate or pressure difference needed for the flow, expected hydrodynamic resistance of the fluidic network.
- Internal volume of the components
- Identification of the sources of dead volume and estimation of the dead volumes
- Identification of the operating pressure and temperature ranges and classification of the device according to application classes defined in ISO22916:2022 where applicable
- Functional performance including required sensing characteristics (resolution, detection limits, etc.), required actuation capabilities of the pumps (flow or pressure range, stability, response time etc.),
- Integration constraints such as number of flow paths within the system, number of sensing and actuation points along the fluidic path, compatibility requirements with external peripherals

4.2. System Architecture

The system architecture defines how sensors, actuators, and fluidic components are arranged and interconnected to form a functional microfluidic system. The architecture should translate the identified requirements into a coherent structure. The design of the system architecture should consider the following aspects:

- System structure: identification of the flow path(s), the components on the flow path(s) forming the system, and the interaction between the components.
- Fluidic network configuration: Sequencing of the components and arrangement of the interconnections between the components (microfluidic device, sensors, actuators, etc.) along the flow path(s), to avoid unnecessary flow path complexity
- Placement of the sensors/actuators: Positioning the sensors/actuators on the flow path considering the upstream and downstream effects (e.g. a sensor may introduce a hydrodynamic resistance to the fluidic network).
- Placement of the functional elements: Positioning of the reservoirs, filters, bubble traps, etc. on the flow path.

- Fluidic routing: Definition of the number of flow paths avoiding unnecessary branching.
- Modularity: Organisation of the system using modular building blocks where applicable to facilitate integration and interoperability as defined in ISO10991:2023.

4.3. Selection of Components

Following the definition of the system architecture, appropriate components shall be selected to fulfil the functional roles identified within the microfluidic system. Component selection shall ensure that each selected element meets the operational requirements and can be integrated within the system architecture. The selection of components should consider the following aspects:

- Sensors: Selection criteria should include sensing resolution, response time, measurement range, and compatibility with the fluid properties and operating conditions, including the connection types.
- Actuators, such as the pumps, should be selected according to the required flow rates, pressure differences, actuation resolution, and compatibility with the fluid properties and operating conditions, including the connection types.
- Functional components such as filters, bubble traps, or reservoirs, should be selected considering their ability to perform the specific function without adversely affecting the system performance by excessively increasing the pressure drop or dead volume.
- Interconnection components such as connectors, fittings, and tubing should be selected to enable reliable fluid transfer between the components. The selected components should provide leak free sealing under identified flow conditions.
- Interoperability: Component specifications should be verified against the system requirements to ensure that the components can operate together.

When available, designers may consult the updated MFMET database on sensors and actuators [Yildirim et al (2026)].

4.4. Compatibility and Interfacing

Compatibility and interfacing shall be considered to ensure reliable integration of sensors, actuators, and fluidic components within the microfluidic system. Interfaces shall enable leak-free fluid transfer, proper alignment of components, and interoperability between devices originating from different sources. ISO 22916 provides interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections, and device classification and should be used as a reference when designing microfluidic interfaces. The following aspects should be considered:

- Fluidic ports: Fluid transfer between components should occur through the ports that allow reliable connection to other devices, connectors, or tubing.
- Port pitch: When multiple ports are present, their spacing should follow the grid defined in ISO 22916 to facilitate interoperability between devices.
- Port diameter: Port diameter should be compatible with the selected port pitch and connection method to allow proper sealing and connection.
- Distance from edges: Ports should be placed at sufficient distance from device edges to allow space for connectors, sealing elements, and mechanical mounting.
- Interfacing area: Surfaces surrounding ports should remain free of structures that could interfere with connectors or sealing elements.
- Clamping zones: Areas intended for mechanical mounting or clamping should be reserved and kept free of microstructures.

- Connection orientation: Devices may use top or side connections depending on the connector type and system configuration.
- Reference point and alignment: Interfaces should be defined relative to a reference point to ensure consistent positioning and alignment of ports and connectors.

4.5. Material Selection

Material selection shall ensure compatibility with the fluids handled by the microfluidic system, the integrated components, and the operating conditions of the application. Material selection should consider the following aspects:

- Chemical compatibility: Materials should be compatible with the fluids handled in the system to avoid degradation or contamination.
- Biocompatibility: For biological applications, materials should be biocompatible to prevent alteration of biological samples or processes.
- Surface properties: Surface characteristics such as wettability, hydrophilicity, or hydrophobicity should be considered as they influence fluid behaviour in microchannels.
- Thermal compatibility: Materials should remain stable within the operating temperature range and exhibit compatible thermal expansion where components are interfaced.
- Mechanical strength: Materials should withstand the expected pressure and mechanical stresses without deformation or leakage.
- Permeability and absorption: Gas permeability or solvent absorption should be evaluated where these properties may influence system performance.

4.6. Environmental and Operating Conditions

The operating environment of the microfluidic system influences the performance and stability of sensors, actuators, and fluidic components. Environmental parameters should therefore be defined and considered during system design to ensure that all components operate within their specified limits. The following aspects should be considered:

- Operating pressure: The system pressure range should remain within the limits of all integrated components. Where applicable, devices may be classified according to the application classes defined in ISO 22916.
- Operating temperature: The expected temperature range should be compatible with the materials, sensors, and actuators used in the system.
- Humidity: Environmental humidity may influence sensor performance, electronic components, and material properties.
- Mechanical vibration: Vibrations originating from pumps, actuators, or external equipment may affect measurement stability or fluidic connections.
- Electromagnetic interference: Electrical disturbances may affect signal integrity of sensors and control electronics.
- Environmental contamination: Dust, particles, or chemical contaminants should not enter the fluidic system or interfere with microfluidic channels.
- Operating environment: The system should be designed considering its intended environment of use (e.g. laboratory, industrial, or field deployment).

4.7. Manufacturability

Design choices should support practical fabrication and reliable assembly of the microfluidic system. The following aspects should be considered:

- **Manufacturing compatibility:** Component designs should be compatible with the selected fabrication methods.
- **Dimensional tolerances:** Dimensions and tolerances should allow proper alignment and fit between interconnected components.
- **Component alignment:** The design should allow accurate positioning of components to ensure correct fluidic connections and sealing.
- **Sealing implementation:** Seals, gaskets, or other sealing elements should be incorporated to provide leak-free interfaces between components.
- **Mechanical mounting:** Appropriate mounting or clamping mechanisms should be provided to maintain stable connections during operation.

4.8. Accessibility and Maintenance

The system design should allow access to key components to support inspection, servicing, and replacement during operation or troubleshooting. The following aspects should be considered:

- **Access to components:** Sensors, actuators, connectors, and other critical components should be reachable for inspection or replacement.
- **Modular replacement:** Components should be arranged so that individual elements can be replaced without disassembling the entire system.
- **Cleaning and flushing:** The fluidic network should allow cleaning or flushing procedures to remove contaminants, bubbles, or residues.
- **Connection accessibility:** Fluidic connectors, tubing, and interfaces should be accessible for installation and replacement.

5. Integration Techniques

The integration of a microfluidic system consists in the assembly of multiple components in order to create one or more continuous fluidic paths throughout the system. Two main categories can be distinguished: monolithic integration, and modular integration. Monolithic integration is achieved by creating a device in a single fabrication pipeline without splitting individual functional units into their own components. Modular integration is achieved by composing complete system from individual components, each comprising a functional unit. Modular integration can be further divided into two sub-categories: permanent and reconfigurable modular integration. Permanent modular integration is achieved by applying permanent bonding techniques to connect components. These techniques include: thermal bonding, chemical bonding, glue and adhesives. Reconfigurable modular integration is defined by the use of reversible integration of components, thereby components can be inserted and removed from the system at will. Reconfigurable integration can be divided into two final categories: tubing-based or tubeless. Tubing-based integration involves the use of tubing and tubing connectors, while tubeless is generally based on mechanical clamping using gaskets and may involve dedicated parts such as clamps, manifolds, and adapters.

Most often a microfluidic system is built up using multiple integration techniques. At each hierarchical level, one should decide what is the most appropriate technique to use. For example, a microfluidic chip can be assembled in a permanent way by bonding different layers into a complete microfluidic

device. This device can then be connected in a modular way by clamping onto a manifold, which on its turn can be connected to a pump by using tubing and connectors.

5.1. Guidance on choice of integration technique

Here we provide guidance on common qualities considered when choosing between the broad categories of integration technique presented above.

Integration classes (listed from high degree of integration to low degree of integration)

- Monolithic
- Modular
 - Permanent
 - Reconfigurable
 - Tubeless
 - Tubing-based

Monolithic Integration:

- **Material Compatibility: Low.** Only materials compatible with the monolithic production process may be used. There are often further strong constraints on which part of the production process can accommodate which materials.
- **Miniaturization Potential: High.** No extra space is required for component interfacing. The length and size of channels connecting functional units can be pushed to physical or manufacturing limits.
- **Design Modularity: Low.** Changing one functional unit for another requires redesign and re-fabrication of the entire system.
- **Dead Volume: Low.** No extra channels are required for component interfacing and the length of channels connecting functional units can be minimized.
- **Automatability: High.** The entire production process can often be standardized. Handling and integration of external components does not need to be considered.
- **Cost:** This approach is often cheapest at high production volume. Setting up a monolithic production line is often very expensive and the design process for a part can be complex, but the high degree of automation and savings on material costs (due to miniaturization) drives down the cost per part at large production volumes.
- **Reliability Against Leakage: High.** There are no bonding interfaces between functional units to leak.

Permanent modular Integration:

- **Material Compatibility: Moderate.** Heterogeneous material integration remains a challenge in the field and often requires some development for new material combinations. Recent advances using thin film adhesives or dispensed liquid adhesives have lowered this challenge, but adhesives add another layer of complexity with respect material compatibility in that compatibility of the adhesive with the operating conditions (e.g. chemical and thermal) must be considered.
- **Miniaturization Potential: Moderate.** No extra space is required for external mechanical clamping, but some extra area is required on the bonding surface for sealing.
- **Modularity: Moderate-Low.** Components are modular at time of manufacture. Material compatibility must be considered and device footprint must be matched to replace one component with another. Standardized device layouts like those covered in ISO 22916 help mitigate this challenge.

- **Dead Volume: Moderate-Low.** While components still require inlet and outlet channels, the interface itself is often low volume when compared to gaskets and tubes.

Automatability: Moderate. Fewer steps require manual intervention than in modular integration, but a wider variety of processes (i.e. component handling and local administration of adhesive) must be brought together than with monolithic approaches.

- **Cost:** This approach is often cheapest at intermediate production volume. The production process is often more expensive to develop from scratch than modular integration, but potentially significantly cheaper than monolithic processes.
- **Reliability Against Leakage: Moderate.** Optimization and automation of bonding can lead to high bond reliability compared to modular approaches which often require some degree of manual assembly.

Tubeless reconfigurable Integration:

- **Material Compatibility: Moderate-High.** For gasket-based interfacing strategies, the gasket must be less stiff than the device itself and any external clamping hardware, but this is often easily achieved. Compatibility of the gasket material with the final chemical operating conditions must also be considered.
- **Miniaturization Potential: Moderate-low.** Extra space is required for external mechanical clamping hardware.
- **Modularity: Moderate-High.** Components can be swapped at point of use. While material compatibility is less difficult than in the case of permanent integration, it must be considered. Component footprint must be matched to replace one component with another. Standardized device layouts like those covered in ISO 22916 help mitigate this challenge.
- **Dead Volume: Moderate.** While components still require inlet and outlet channels, the interface itself is often low volume when compared to tubes and often only slightly larger in volume when compared to permanent integration.
- **Automatability: Moderate-Low.** Manual assembly is often required, and the task of full automation can be significantly more difficult due to the need to install clamping hardware.
- **Cost:** This approach is often cheapest at small production volumes. When in the prototyping phase or when producing products in batches that are too small to warrant automation, tubeless integration can be faster and easier than permanent integration or tubing-based approaches.
- **Reliability Against Leakage: Moderate.** Optimization of gasket pocket tolerances and clamping hardware determine seal reliability. Manual assembly still introduces some risk of mis-assembly and thereby leakage.

Tubing-Based reconfigurable Integration:

- **Material Compatibility: Moderate-High.** The relative stiffness of the devices and components of the interface must be considered. The tube itself is often used as the compliant sealing material. The compatibility of the tubing and fitting materials must be considered with respect to the final operating conditions.
- **Miniaturization Potential: low.** Tubing must run between components and minimum bend radii of tubing must be respected. For cases when a fitting must be used, area in the device footprint must be spent on the interfacing between the fitting and the device.
- **Modularity: High.** Components can be swapped at point of use. While material compatibility is simpler than in the case of permanent integration, it must be considered. One device need not share a footprint with another to replace it.

- **Dead Volume: High.** Components still require inlet and outlet channels, and on top of this the volume of the tubing is generally several times larger than that introduced by the other discussed interfacing approaches.
- **Automatability: Low.** Manual assembly is often required when attaching tubing to a device.
- **Cost:** This approach can be the cheapest for very small batches. No manifold or clamping hardware need be designed unlike tubeless approaches. It is often employed for small batches when one needs to iterate a few times very quickly and/or must interface between devices designed for otherwise incompatible connector/fitting types.
- **Reliability Against Leakage: Moderate-Low.** Optimization of tubing interface tolerances determine seal reliability. Manual assembly still introduces some risk of mis-assembly. Tubing path must be well managed (or strain-relief included) to avoid breaking of the fluidic seal when tubes are moved.

Note: for some specific applications special considerations must also be applied to interfacing similar to those covered in section 3 and 4 of this document. Examples include:

- **Safety:** Presence of dangerous or toxic materials may lead a designer to favour higher degrees of integration to preclude any chance that a user may come in contact with the dangerous material
- **Signal Fidelity:** Connections between sensors and readout equipment may need to be kept short. Modular connection technologies may not be present. Both of these possibilities may require the designer to use monolithic integration.
- **Mechanical robustness:** Sometime the presence of a high vibration use environment favours the use of full integration or the use of external mechanical clamping
- **Gas Permeability:** for applications where specific dissolved gas concentrations must be well maintained, the gas permeability of interfacing materials must be carefully considered.

6. Control Systems

This section provides general guidance for implementing and maintaining microfluidic control systems including: general classification, considerations for documentation, calibration and testing.

6.1. Types of Control

A control system should be categorized as either closed-loop or open-loop. Closed-loop control systems are those which require the use of both sensors and actuators for control while open-loop control systems only require the use of actuators for control. As such, for closed-loop systems, the guidance in this section applies to both sensors and actuators while for open-loop systems the guidance may only apply to actuators.

NOTE: Systems implementing open-loop control may also include sensors outside of the control system (for example, for process monitoring).

6.2. Controlled Quantities

For a given microfluidic system, the physical quantities which are being controlled should be clearly identified and documented.

Common examples include:

- Flowrate
- Temperature
- Pressure
- Chemical concentration

6.3. Acceptable Limits

For a given controlled quantity, acceptable limits on its value and behavior over time should be established and documented. Depending on the application, regular testing of the system to ensure that parameters are within limits may be required.

Common examples of limits include:

- Allowable range for the controlled quantity
- Allowable drift over a stated time period
- Settling time

6.4. Calibration and Performance Testing

Regular performance testing of the entire setup as well as calibration of sensors/actuators can help ensure that the system continues to function as designed. This may be required depending on the application.

Testing and calibration activities can include:

- Testing compliance with acceptable limits across the full operational envelope
- Calibration of individual components
- Calibration of the entire control system

6.5. Software and Firmware

While purely hardware-based control is possible, control systems often require digital control. When choosing and maintaining software/firmware, the following recommendations apply:

- prefer standardized and validated software
- prefer open-source solutions
- prefer standardized digital communication protocols
- maintain records of software and firmware versions
- use version control for custom software

6.6. Documentation

Documentation supports traceability, repeatability, and transfer of the setup between users or sites. The type of documentation required depends on the application.

Common documentation includes:

- SOPs for usage, testing and calibration

- Limits on the operational envelope
- Records of test results
- Records of calibration results including traceability

7. Reproducibility and Quality Assurance

7.1. Calibration and Validation

Establish routine calibration protocols for the specific quantity to measure, according to relevant technical standards to ensure consistent sensor and actuator performance. Several examples relevant to this field follow.

EURAMET guide cg 27 and EURAMET technical guide nº 4 provide information on calibration methods for several metrological quantities (Flow rate, volume, flow resistivity). For general validation methodology in order to comply with point 5.4.5 of ISO/IEC 17025 standard means that the laboratories “shall validate non-standard methods, laboratory designed/developed methods, standard methods used outside their intended scope, and amplifications and modifications of standard methods to confirm that the methods are fit for the intended use”. Several validation methodologies can be found in the Eurachem Guide: The Fitness for Purpose of Analytical Methods

-A Laboratory Guide to Method Validation and Related Topics or in EUROLAB - Validation of Test Methods / General Principles and Concepts EL1545/96 .

- Validate the integration setup through reproducibility tests across multiple devices and operational cycles. This validation will be done by an intercomparison between partners and by computational simulation.

7.2. Documentation and Traceability

Traceability ensures that a measurement result or the value of the standard is related to references through an unbroken chain of comparisons. A calibration laboratory “establishes traceability of its own measurement standards and instruments to the SI by means of an unbroken chain of calibrations or comparisons linking them to relevant primary standards of the SI units of measurement.”

Linking calibration to SI units is done through national measurement standards, which may be primary standards. SI units are primary standards when tethered to fundamental physical constants. All test equipment requiring calibration should undergo an initial calibration before being put into service.

The use recognise calibration services and reference compounds providers (Accredited laboratories of National Metrology Institutes) is recommended to ensure the traceability of any measurements.

It is also best practice to maintain detailed records of component specifications, integration procedures, calibration data, and operational parameters.

8. Conclusion

The integration of sensors, actuators, and fluidic components in microfluidic devices requires careful selection, design, and assembly practices aligned with ISO 22916:2022. Emphasizing compatibility and reproducibility ensures reliable device performance, facilitates standardization, and supports scalable manufacturing. Adhering to these guidelines will promote effective integration and consistent operation within microfluidic systems.

9. References

- AAMI TIR 101:2021 - Fluid delivery performance testing for infusion pumps
- EURAMET calibration guide no.27 - Guidelines for the Calibration of Drug Delivery Devices and Infusion Device Analysers, version 2.0 (02/2026)
- EURAMET technical guide no.4 - Evaluation of flow-related quantities in microfluidic devices, version 1.0 (05/2024)
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- IEC 60601-2-24:2012 - Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-24: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of infusion pumps and controllers
- IEC 61499 The Industrial Automation Standard for Portability
- IEC 62304:2006 - Medical device software
- IEC 62321 - Determination of certain substances in electrotechnical products
- IEC 63177:2024 Test methods for compatibility of construction materials with electrical insulating liquids
- IEEE 1451 smart transducer interface standards
- ISO 22916:2022 Microfluidic devices - Interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections and initial device classification
- SEMI MS11 - Specification for Microfluidic Port and Pitch Dimensions
- SEMI MS6 - Guide for Design and Materials for Interfacing Microfluidic Systems
- SEMI MS7 - Specification for Microfluidic Interfaces to Electronic Device Packages
- SEMI MS9 - Specification for High Density Permanent Connections Between Microfluidic Devices
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